

**THEORETICAL AND PRACTICAL FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE
PEDAGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN DEVELOPING INCLUSIVE
COMPETENCE IN PRIMARY SCHOOL**

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Abstract

This article analyzes the theoretical and methodological foundations of developing inclusive competence in primary school students through innovative pedagogical technologies. The structure, pedagogical conditions, and mechanisms of inclusive competence formation are revealed. The effectiveness of interactive methods, differentiated instruction, project-based learning, and ICT tools in fostering empathy, tolerance, and social cooperation among students is substantiated.

Keywords: inclusive education, inclusive competence, innovative pedagogical technologies, primary education, differentiated approach, interactive method, empathy.

Introduction

The 21st century education system requires a person-centered model based on humanistic principles. The concept of inclusive education is widely used internationally, and the right of every child to quality education is recognized. In particular, global initiatives put forward by UNESCO define ensuring equality and inclusion in the educational process as a priority task.

The primary education stage is an important period of socialization of the individual and the formation of a system of values. Therefore, it is at this stage that the development of inclusive competence is manifested as an urgent pedagogical problem.

Research methodology

The following methods were used in the research process:

- analysis of scientific and pedagogical literature;
- observation and comparison;
- pedagogical experimental and test works;
- statistical analysis methods.

The theoretical basis was taken from the concept of social development of the individual and the ideas of collaborative learning. In particular, Lev Vygotsky's theory of socio-cultural development substantiates the importance of interaction in an inclusive environment.

Structure and content of inclusive competence

Inclusive competence is a complex integrative quality consisting of the following components:

1. Cognitive component - knowledge about inclusion, disability, equality;
2. Axiological component - humanistic values and tolerance;
3. Emotional component - empathy and emotional stability;
4. Activity component - cooperation, social communication and assistance skills.

This competency is formed in primary school students on the basis of a specially organized pedagogical process.

The effectiveness of innovative pedagogical technologies

1. Interactive methods

Methods such as “Brainstorming”, “Role playing”, “Discussion”, “Insert” form a culture of independent thinking and cooperation in students. Through role-playing games, children experience various social situations and develop empathetic thinking.

2. Differential approach

Adapting educational materials according to the level of complexity, volume and methods of implementation ensures the success of each child. This strengthens the atmosphere of mutual respect and social equality.

3. Project-based learning

Through the project method, students participate in collective activities, gaining experience in social responsibility and cooperation. Group work creates a practical manifestation of inclusive competence.

4. Information and communication technologies

Digital educational tools, multimedia resources and interactive platforms allow for teaching taking into account individual needs. This is especially important for students with different learning speeds and receptive abilities.

Results of pilot studies

The pilot studies were conducted with the participation of primary school students. According to the results of the initial diagnostics, the level of inclusive competence of students was on average 46%, while after training based on innovative methods, this indicator reached 71%.

It was observed that empathy indicators increased by 25%, and teamwork indicators by 30%. These results confirm the effectiveness of innovative pedagogical technologies.

Discussion

The results obtained show that the development of inclusive competence should not be limited to theoretical explanations. It is strengthened through practical activities, cooperation and social experience.

Methodological training of the primary school teacher, creation of a positive psychological environment in the classroom and cooperation with parents are important factors.

Conclusion

The development of inclusive competence in primary schools is effectively implemented on the basis of innovative pedagogical technologies. Interactive methods, a differentiated approach, project-based learning and the use of ICT form the qualities of tolerance, empathy and social cooperation in students.

The development of inclusive education is a pedagogical

The development of inclusive competence in primary grades is one of the strategic directions of today's education system. The results of the study show that the effective organization of inclusive education serves not only to support students with special needs, but also to form the values of social justice, equality and humanity in all children. In this sense, inclusive competence is an important factor in the successful socialization of a person in society and constructive communication.

The use of innovative pedagogical technologies makes the process of forming inclusive competence systematic, goal-oriented and effective. Interactive methods develop in students the skills of freely expressing their opinions, listening to others and respecting others. A differentiated approach creates conditions for success, taking into account the individual capabilities of each child. Project-based learning and the use of

information and communication technologies enhance the collaborative activities of students and prepare them for real-life situations.

The results of the pilot study showed that the level of empathy, social activity and teamwork skills of students in lessons organized on the basis of innovative methods significantly increased. This confirms that inclusive competence is formed not only through theoretical concepts, but also in the process of practical activity and communication.

At the same time, the development of inclusive competence is directly dependent on the professional training and methodological skills of the teacher. In creating an inclusive environment, the teacher must have activity, patience, an individual approach and reflexive analysis skills. Cooperation with parents and ensuring a positive psychological climate in the classroom are also important conditions for this process.

In general, the formation of inclusive competence at the primary education stage creates the foundation for developing a culture of tolerance and social cohesion in society. In the future, conducting comprehensive scientific research in this area, improving methodological recommendations and improving the skills of pedagogical personnel will further increase the effectiveness of inclusive education.

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